

Translation as Mirror Image in *Silence! The Court Is In Session*

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Abstract

This research paper delves into the complexities of Vijay Tendulkar's seminal play, *Shantata! Court Chalu Ahe*, which has been translated into English as *Silence! The Court is in Session* by Priya Adarkar. The play, originally written in 1963 and published in 1967, serves as a poignant reflection of the challenges faced by women in orthodox Indian society. Tendulkar's narrative challenges the entrenched values and customs of a deeply traditional society, offering a stark portrayal of the struggles and sufferings of women, particularly within the confines of an authoritarian societal structure.

Through a nuanced analysis of Tendulkar's work, this paper seeks to explore the multidimensional aspects of human nature and societal constraints depicted in *Silence! The Court is in Session*. The study employs a qualitative research approach, utilizing textual analysis and drawing upon various literary theories to uncover the underlying themes and messages embedded in the play. By examining Tendulkar's portrayal of individual autonomy and societal oppression, this paper aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the human condition and the complexities of societal structures in the context of modern India.

The findings of this research shed light on Tendulkar's critique of societal norms and his exploration of human potentialities within the framework of an orthodox society. The paper concludes by emphasizing the enduring relevance of Tendulkar's work in contemporary discourse, particularly in its exploration of gender dynamics, societal constraints, and the resilience of the human spirit.

Keywords: orthodox, authoritarian, unambiguous, unequivocal etc.

Introduction

Vijay Tendulkar (1928-2008) stands out as a prominent postmodern playwright in Indian English Literature, renowned for his staunch advocacy of humanity and human dignity. He emerged as a rebel against the entrenched values, customs, and traditions of a deeply orthodox society, notably with his groundbreaking production of *Shantata! Court Chalu Ahe (Silence! The Court is in Session)* in 1967. The play features Leela Benare as the main character, whose life within the play mirrors the drama of real life.

Historical context of *silence! The court is in session*:

Set in post-Independence India, a period marked by the ratification of the constitution and India's transition into a democratic nation, "Silence! The Court is in Session" reflects the societal milieu of the time. Despite the euphoria of independence in 1947, women's rights often took a backseat to broader national concerns. Tendulkar's play serves as a mirror to middle-class society, illuminating the challenges faced by women. The character of Leela Benare, a working woman, becomes the focal point of the narrative, highlighting the plight of women in orthodox societies.

Exposition of the Vulnerability of Women

Silence! The Court is in Session unfolds as a mock trial of Miss Leela Benare, a simple and earnest school teacher. Throughout the trial, she is subjected to ridicule and mockery, accused of infanticide and engaging in an illicit relationship with a married man, Professor Damle. The other characters, including Mr. Gopal Pokshe, Mr. Karnik, Rokde, Samant, the defense and crown counsels, Mr. Sukhatme, and the judge, Mr. Kashikar, all participate in this charade, reflecting the malicious nature of society's underbelly.

The members of this group represent various strata of society, and their spiteful treatment of Leela Benare exposes their hypocrisy and double standards. The orchestrated conspiracy against her, under the guise of a mock trial, serves to dissect and expose her personal life, highlighting the dark realities of middle-class society.

The play exposes the vulnerability of women in the traditional Indian society. She is, practically, made the victim of the cruel game very cunningly maneuvered by her fellow actors; her private life is exposed gleefully and strangely. The charge of infanticide, brought against her at the beginning of the mock trial, turns in to a verdict against her at the end, mainly because cotemporary insular. Indian society cannot allow the birth of a child out of wedlock. In an interview the writer himself says that "Human beings are like Mickey Mouse and Kin, fighting for survival, in this battle one mouse kills another. Many mice gang up and end up ruthlessly destroying one another. I see this as a blind justice." (Batra 37). It shows that judicial system become the face of a very repressive and dehumanized system if the person involved in the process of justice are themselves devoid of human values and compassion. They are outwardly decent folk and don't suspect that they have this dark sides.

Miss Leela Benare is summoned merely as a witness while Miss Benare remains the prime accused as the mother of an illegitimate child and having illicit relations with so many persons. As the trial go on all the witnesses and authorities become inimical towards Miss Leela Benare. On the charge of unmarried motherhood and having illicit relations with so many persons, the judge, Mr. Kashikar orders the school authorities to dismiss such an immoral woman. Miss Leela Benare tried to defend herself through a long soliloquy. "The parrot to the sparrow said, "why, of why, are your eyes so red?" Oh, my dear friend, what shall I say" Someone has stolen my great nest away. Sparrow, sparrow, poor little sparrow 'oh brother

crow, oh, brother crow. Were you there? Did you see it go?" No, I don't know I didn't see, what are your troubles to do with me? O sparrow, sparrow." (Tendulkar 78)

The play is based on the theme of power, its sources and manifestation. The character fights for authority and power and try to trap each other through a metaphorical mock-court. But peculiarly, the power, play that underscores the games operates more through the monologues rather than through the dialogues. The play oscillates between the atricalization of private life and privatization of theatrical performance. While performing the role of a woman in the group, Leela transcends the limitations of verbal reasoning and tries to spy into the masculine strategies. The Charges against Leela Benare are leveled by evidences of reality that mark out the boundaries what might be called the collective mindscape, the limits of same experience.

Leela differs as to the best way to break loose from this enslavement to collective prejudice, but she believes that truth and reality are achieved only when reality is approached in nakedness of mind. Leela's argument against body and its mechanical connections and her discourse of emotion saves her from dehumanization. Vijay Tendulkar again and again mentions society and social customs by his characters. Miss Benare has the charge of infanticide. Mr. Kashikar, the judge enquires Sukhatme, "Did you notice, also, Sukhatme, that this charge is important from the social point of view? The question of infanticide is one of great social significance. That is why I deliberately picked it. We consider society's best interests in all we do" (Tendulkar 26.) Miss Benare, the heroine of the play, is a school teacher. She is totally devoted to her profession and her popularity has caused the envy of her colleagues at school and even the school management. She is never late to her school. She uses to stand while teaching. She says, "I never sit when teaching. That's how I keep my eye on the whole class. No one has a chance to play up. MY class is scared stiff of me! And they adore me, too. My children will do anything for me. For I'd give the last drop of my blood to teach them." (58)

The woman who is an accused has made a heinous bolt on the sacred brow of motherhood-which is purer than heaven itself. For that, any punishment, however great, that the law may give her will be too mild by far. The character of the accused is appalling. It is bankrupt of morality. The accused is public enemy number one. If such socially destructive tendencies are encouraged to flourish, this country and its culture will be totally destroyed.

Sukhatme further clarifies his point 'Infanticide is a dreadful act, but bunging an illegitimate child is horrifying. If it is encouraged, there will no such thing as the institution of marriage. Immorality will flourish. Before, our eyes, our beautiful dream of society, governed by tradition will crumble into dust.' (Tendulkar 70) It is through his character that Vijay Tendulkar expresses his deep concern about motherhood, morality, society, tradition and our religion.

Who is under attack here?

Tendulkar has criticized the middle class morality that throttles the tender desires of Benare, a middle class woman, to mother a child in the play. Tendulkar seems to leave the play without suggesting any solution to the problem. None in the play is ready to sympathize with Benare. Only Mr. Kashikar, the judge, feels that they are going too far in their mock-trial but, then, he immediately silence his conscience. After all the Court is in session and everyone is expected to keep silence!

Silence! The Court is in Session not a propaganda play. It grapples with several problems of the Indian society – such as the degradation of the judiciary system, pretentious institutional social service organizations, and forceful male supremacy in Indian society, in a masterful way. However, the fact is that we look at the world and our friends, relatives, and value their roles only from their utility towards our ends. Conventional morality is only an imaginary issue.

Proverbs and subjugation of women in the play

The play includes different proverbs which pertain to different themes. There are a few selected proverbs which directly relate to women either glorifying or humiliating them. The first instance of the proverb related to women appears to be glorifying them. Because Ms. Benare is charged of infanticide, every character in the court starts glorifying the role of a mother. Mr. Sukhatme starts making grounds for his arguments by glorifying motherhood using a Sanskrit proverb “*Matrudevo Bhava*” (Tendulkar 37) in which a mother is given the status of a God. “Be thy mother as a God” (Tendulkar 30). Mr. Sukhatme begins his opening statement with persuading quotes about mother and her role in order to form base for his arguments. He tries to glorify mother as holy and honourable to make his allegations firm.

While Mr. Sukhatme is presenting his arguments, he is interrupted by Mr. Kashikar who quotes another Sanskrit proverb “*Janani Janmabhūmis chasvargadapigariyasi*” (Tendulkar 30) which means that the mother and the nation are higher than the heaven. “Mother and the motherland both are even higher than heaven” (Tendulkar 30). By using this proverb, Mr. Kashikar tries to support Mr. Sukhatme’s argument that mother is the noblest of all human beings and Ms. Benare has spoiled the image of a mother by killing her child thus darkening the image of a mother.

When everyone gives information about Ms. Benare, Mr. Sukhatme concludes that Ms. Benare’s crime is very grave and it affects the society very badly. He questions whether women should be allowed to be free or not. As a result of freedom, Ms. Benare crossed the cultural borders hence he concludes that *Na striswatantryamarhati* (Tendulkar 71) “women is not fit for independence” (Tendulkar 71). It is not claimed here that women should be given ultimate freedom but they should not be suppressed under the cause of social harmony.

In the end, Ms. Benare is given an opportunity to say something about the allegation against her. She tells that she has been quiet for many years but now she wants to express her thoughts. According to her, each and every moment in life should be enjoyed nevertheless; she complains about life as “Life is not worthy of life” (Tendulkar 73). She blames people for wasting their time in futile things than enjoying life. She puts a question to all that when God has offered us a life is treachery. It is a decomposing book, a venomous snake which bites itself. Life is something and something is nothing. She says, *Na jeevanjeevanmarhati* (Tendulkar 73) because we are unable to live life according to our desire. We have to keep our wishes aside and live life according to the norms of the society because we are bound by the socio-cultural ethics. Ms. Benare says that body is the only thing which is primary and emotions are secondary in the society. She questions why women have to make adjustments every time. If it is so then life is not life at all.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Vijay Tendulkar's *Silence! The Court is in Session* masterfully exposes the vulnerability of women in traditional Indian society through a humanist lens. The play's title, *Shantata!*

Court Chalu Ahe, underscores the absolute authority of the judiciary, often used to stifle dissent and maintain societal norms.

The trial of Miss Leela Benare serves as a poignant example of this vulnerability, as she is subjected to mockery and ridicule, her private life dissected and exposed. The play's portrayal of the malevolent nature of society's underbelly reflects Tendulkar's deep-seated critique of societal hypocrisy and double standards.

Moreover, *Silence! The Court is in Session* is not merely a depiction of a mock trial; it is a reflection of the broader societal attitudes towards women and their agency. The play's exploration of power dynamics, gender roles, and societal constraints makes it a timeless piece of literature that continues to resonate with audiences today.

In essence, Tendulkar's play serves as a stark reminder of the challenges faced by women in patriarchal societies, urging us to confront and address these issues with compassion and empathy.

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